

A history of rice in Laos*

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Most historians trace the origins of the Lao nation-state back to 1353, the date of the coronation of Fa Ngum as the first ruler of the kingdom (mandala) of Lan Xang. The history of rice in what is now known as Laos predates the founding of Lan Xang, however, by thousands of years.

Although the history of the ethnic diversity of what is now known as Laos is generally well documented (Dommen 1995, Simms and Simms 1999, Stuart-Fox 1998), the history of some aspects of rice cultivation within the area is still open to conjecture. What is accepted, however, is that rice has been cultivated in the region for a long time. This is reflected in linguistic evidence where, in the Lao language, as in several other languages in the Asian region, the words for rice and food are synonymous. Anthropological studies in northeast Thailand have provided evidence of rice cultivation from pottery imprints of grain and husks of *Oryza sativa* dated to at least 2,000 BC and probably older (Khush 1997, White 1997). Palaeoenvironmental evidence suggests the presence of even older plant cultivation in the middle Mekong basin (White et al 2004), although the precise crops grown have yet

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to be determined. In a review of "the peopling and prehistory of Laos," Stuart-Fox (1998) suggests that rice was cultivated, using broadcasting techniques, along the margins of ponds and streams by small settlements in the area, from the late fourth and early third millennia BC. It is conjectured that, before the deliberate cultivation of rice in the region, harvesting of the grain of its wild rice progenitors probably took place (Harlan 1995, Oka 1988, Vaughan 1994, White 1995).

"Wet"-rice cultivation in the lowlands of Laos and neighboring countries has long been associated with ethnic groups connected with the main linguistic group of the region, the Tai. The Tai, in their area of origin in southern China, probably already had a staple diet of wet rice. They built their villages in river valleys where there was plenty of water and level ground that could be flooded in the growing season (Simms and Simms 1999). Golomb (1976) also supports the belief that the Tai were traditionally wet-rice cultivators in their ancestral homeland.

Stuart-Fox (1998) and Higham (2002) indicate that, as early as 500 BC, the local population in what is now known as the Khorat Plateau of northeast Thailand was using domesticated buffalo and iron-tipped plows for wet-rice cultivation. He suggests that, despite a lack of systematic evidence to date, similar agricultural developments likely occurred on the plains of the Lao provinces of Vientiane, Khammouane, and Savannakhet. When the Tai people moved into what now constitutes Laos, Thailand, and upper Myanmar, they brought with them their own wet-rice cultivation practices.

The Tai-Lao currently form the dominant linguistic group in several provinces of Laos, including Vientiane, Luang Prabang, Khammouane, Savannakhet, and Champassak (Batson 1991). Other Tai groups that live in Laos are the Tai-Leu of Luang Prabang and areas to the north, the Tai-Neua of Houaphanh, and the Tai-Dam (Black Tai) and Tai-Deng (Red Tai) of Phongsaly and Houaphanh. Of the Austroasiatic groups who live in the adjoining uplands,

the Kasseng, Loven, Souay, and Bru are the larger groups inhabiting southern Laos, while the Lamet and Khmou are the major groups in the north. The largest single grouping of the Mon-Khmer comprises the Khmou, now concentrated in parts of Luang Prabang, Houaphanh, and Oudomxay provinces. The existence of canals and reservoirs in the southern Lao province of Champassak suggests that lowland irrigated rice cultivation was the principal sustenance crop in southern Laos during the period of Khmer dominance from the 5th to 11th centuries CE.

It is therefore reasonable to assume that, for the last two millennia, the main form of rice cultivation in what is now Laos was wet-rice cultivation in the lowlands. Just when dryland rice cultivation, which is found in the upland environment of Laos and neighboring countries, developed is a matter of conjecture. Khush (1997) suggests that early rice crops in the Asian arc were "probably grown by direct seeding and without standing water." Harlan (1995) also infers that, at least in the areas of original domestication of rice in Asia, wet-rice cultivation is a relatively more recent production method than dryland cultivation techniques. However, White (1995) argues on ecological grounds that dryland rice cultivation must have emerged from initial domestication in a wetland environment. The process of soil puddling and transplanting of seedlings seems to have originated in China and been brought to Southeast Asia (including Laos) through migration. It should be noted, however, that the last ethnic groups to arrive in Laos, the Hmong and Mien

(Yao), who settled in the highlands of Laos in the 19th and early 20th centuries, brought with them dryland rice cultivation practices (Dommen 1995).

Laos and the origins of cultivated Asiatic rice

Though rice cultivation in Laos may date back only to the second millennium BCE, it should be acknowledged that Laos lies within the broader region of likely domestication of Asiatic rice (*Oryza sativa*) (Chang 1976, Oka 1988). Laos is also believed to be near the center of origin of glutinous rice (Golomb 1976, Watabe 1967). Laos is still rich in genetic diversity of wild and weedy rice, with 6 of the known 21 species of wild rice still to be found in the country: *O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. minuta*, *O. officinalis*, *O. ridleyi*, and *O. granulata* (Kuroda et al. Two of these, *O. nivara* and *O. rufipogon*, are the generally accepted progenitors of Asian rice, *O. sativa* (Chang 1976, Oka 1988, Yamanaka et al 2003). Weedy rice, believed to be the interspecific hybrids between the cultivated rice species (*O. sativa*) and wild rice species, has also been commonly observed in Laos.

Historical evidence for the quality of Lao rice

Reference to the quality of rice produced in Laos comes from historical records from the early 1660s, when the description of Laos by an Italian Jesuit priest who worked in the country between 1642 and 1648 was published. The account by Father Givvani Maria Leria was first published in Italian in 1663 (de Marini 1998). The description of rice (and other matters of interest) on both banks of the Mekong River runs as follows:

“However, one must understand that this part of the kingdom, west of the river, is not as prosperous or as fertile as that in the east which greatly surpasses in all respects. The elephants are bigger and stronger there, better trained and more suitable for warfare. The unicorns (rhinoceroses) are also better there than elsewhere. The staple rice is incomparable there and it has a characteristic odour and wildness that is specific to all that grows in this eastern part of the kingdom. There, forests and trees are high, straight and almost all durable, a quality which those growing on the eastern side of this river do not possess: there the virtue of the unicorns is not at all comparable to that of the eastern side. The rice is so hard that one could never boil it and the

wood, badly shaped and twisted—it is more suitable for making smoke than fire. There is a kind of a small strait—it is like the center and middle of the kingdom—which produced such excellent rice that I do not believe that it has its equal anywhere else in the Orient” (de Marini 1998, p 4-5).

Ngaosyvanthn and Ngaosyvanthn (1998) also cite other sources from the 18th century saying that “this country produces abundantly the best kind of rice.” Reference is also made to the royal paddy fields established by the last king of Vientiane, Chao Anouvong (1804-28), within an 18-km wall encircling the city. The occupying Thai armies of 1827 were reportedly surprised at how well endowed Vientiane was with rice. The royal rice fields were apparently still discernible more than 60 years later.

Rice-based power

Following the settlement of the Tai-Lao in the lowland areas in what now comprises Laos, and northeast Thailand, there evolved a number of small political centers known as muang, which were concentrations of social, economic, and military power. Stuart-Fox (1998) reports that the earliest of these Tai muang “of more than local extent” on the upper Mekong “probably dates from no earlier than the 11th century.” These muang were generally centered in valley areas from where they controlled surrounding territory. Control over areas of reliable food production provided the basis of muang power for hundreds of years. The four oldest and strongest muang in what constitutes modern-day Laos were centered on what are currently the provinces of Luang Prabang, Xieng Khouang, Vientiane, and

Champassak. All exercised domination over rice-growing areas that produced significant surpluses (Whitmore 1970).

The decision, in 1560, of King Xetthathirât of Lan Xang to move the royal court from Luang Prabang (or Xieng Thong as it was called at that time) to Vientiane was partly based on the growing food needs (mainly rice) of the administrative center. As well as being at the crossroads for much overland commerce, compared with Luang Prabang, Vientiane lay in a much larger rich and fertile plain well suited to wet-rice cultivation (Simms and Simms 1999).

The significance of rice politically was demonstrated during the rule of Chao Anou, King of Vientiane (1805-28), who led the Lao war of independence against Siam (Thailand) in 1827-28. After Chao Anou's initial defeat, he returned to Vientiane, where he found a Siamese garrison in control of the only available rice supplies. Conflict again broke out between the Siamese and the Lao, leading to Chao Anou's capture and death, and the final destruction of Vientiane (Stuart-Fox 1998).

Rice and French colonialism

During the period of French colonialism in Laos (1893-1945), although coffee and potato growing were introduced to the Boloven Plateau in the south of the country, little effort was made to improve production of the staple crops of rice and maize (McCoy 1970). Almost 100% of the rice produced was grown under rainfed conditions and thereby subject to the vagaries of the weather, with periodic droughts affecting both upland and lowland crops, and periodic flooding occasionally devastating wet-

season lowland rice and other crops grown in areas adjacent to the Mekong River and its tributaries. Production for most of this period did not exceed 350,000 t annually (equal to about 1 kg of rice per day per person for the population of that time) (Gunn 1990). An exception was in 1923 when production was reported to have reached a high of 500,000 t. Gunn (1990) reports that, for most of the period of French colonialism, Laos was a net rice-importing country, with only the Champassak area consistently producing a rice surplus. One of the few inter-

ventions by the French to address the chronic rice deficit during the time of their administration of Laos was to actually ban the export of rice in 1936 (Gunn 1990, Stuart-Fox 1997). This was in response to a drop in the estimated harvest from about 258,000 t in 1935 to about 204,000 t in 1936 (the cause of this reduction is not indicated but, as it was mainly from the traditional rice-exporting provinces adjacent to the Mekong River, it is likely to have been severe flooding). The rice deficit was of such a magnitude in Thakek Province (Khammouane) that there was a fear of starvation. At the time, emergency supplies of rice were requested by the Résident Supérieur from Tonkin and Annam (Gunn 1990).

USAID

The period 1955 to 1963 was a time when the per capita U.S. assistance to Laos exceeded, several fold, that given to other countries in the region. However, very little was spent on agriculture, although more than 90% of the population at that time was farmers (Stuart-Fox 1997). During the 1960s and early 1970s, agricultural development and efforts to achieve rice self-sufficiency were of minor importance in comparison to the escalating military conflict. In 1969 and 1970, USAID did undertake the evaluation of a number of introduced lines and varieties from IRRI, together with some well-known traditional varieties. The lines and varieties from IRRI would have been some of the earliest available, as the institution was established only in 1960. Early multilocation yield trials were undertaken in the provinces of Sayabouly, Khammouane, Luang Prabang, Vientiane, and Sedone (Sedone Province

was later incorporated into the province of Cham-passak). Seed multiplication of several of these IRRI lines and varieties was undertaken for distribution at the Salakham Rice Research Station near the capital, Vientiane, in the 1973 wet season. In addition to the IRRI material (which included both glutinous and nonglutinous lines, the latter including IR22 and IR24), the Lao traditional glutinous variety Do nang nouan and the Thai glutinous variety Sanpatong were also multiplied and distributed to farmers. Some of these varieties were still being grown on a limited scale in the mid-1990s, being known as American rice, reflecting their origins as part of the USAID seed distribution program (Appa Rao et al 2000). Apart from the limited work on the introduction and distribution of rice varieties, little other agricultural development took place during this period because of the displacement of large parts of the population in many areas by the war, and the associated disruption of normal cropping cycles.

Socialist assistance 1977-90

Vietnam

In support of the agricultural cooperatives that were established from 1978 to 1984 in an attempt to improve agricultural productivity, Vietnamese agricultural advisers introduced and evaluated many improved lowland rice varieties from Vietnam. Most of these introductions were nonglutinous and many had IRRI parentage. However, few of the Vietnamese introductions were actually adopted by Lao farmers because of their poorer eating qualities relative to the traditional Lao varieties. One of the Vietnamese introductions, CR203, did become popular for the production of rice noodles and brewing of Lao beer. In 2002, it was still being grown on a limited scale.

USSR

Although large numbers of advisers from the socialist block countries (particularly Russia) were present in Laos during the late 1970s and 1980s,

these advisers and related assistance programs had little influence on agricultural production. The advisers did undertake serious soil surveys and soil-mapping exercises during this time, the results of which were later used for the production of more standardized USDA-type soil maps that, in turn, were used for land-use planning purposes in the late 1990s. In 1982-84, in collaboration with USSR experts, a number of field trials were undertaken on rice, focusing on yield responses to fertilizer inputs. These studies were part of the soil classification mapping exercises.

The rise and fall of agricultural cooperatives: 1978-88

The most significant change relating to rice production in the period immediately after the Lao People's Revolutionary Party (LPRP) came to power in December 1975 was the adoption of a policy for the "collectivization of agricultural production" through the formation of "agricultural cooperatives." This was seen as the most appropriate strategy for "revolutionizing the country, both socially and technologically." The history of the "rise and fall" of these cooperatives has been reviewed in detail by Stuart-Fox (1980) and Evans (1988, 1995). As reported by Evans, the "experiment with collectivization was associated with attempts by the new government to revive the Lao economy following its collapse due to the flight of both capital and business entrepreneurs." It was hoped to use agricultural

cooperatives as the basis for quickly increasing rice production to alleviate a serious and chronic rice deficit in the country. At the time, Laos was importing approximately 15% of its rice requirements. It was believed that cooperatives were the only way peasant agriculture could overcome natural calamities and achieve national food self-sufficiency (Evans 1995). To support these objectives, controls were placed on the price of a range of agricultural commodities, including rice.

Although the policy to create production-based collectives was announced soon after the change of government in 1975, it was not implemented until 1978, following a severe drought in 1977 that further aggravated the already serious rice deficit in the country. The focus of the move to cooperative-based production was in areas of lowland rice cultivation (mainly rainfed, as there was only a very small area of irrigated rice at the time the cooperatives were formed) in provinces with large lowland rice-growing areas in the Mekong River Valley, and in some northern provinces where the LPRP had a strong political base (particularly the provinces of Xieng Khouang, Houaphanh, and Phongsaly). A characteristic of the cooperatives was that they were generally small "village-level" initiatives involving an average of 30 to 40 families, rather than large area collectives. Although a few numbered over 200 families, generally such large cooperatives were not encouraged. The initial basis for the formation and operation of the early cooperatives was at a low level, involving the establishment of labor exchange units that could be used in a coordinated calendar of rice production. Members of the cooperative were expected to contribute their cultivated land for the cooperative's use (while property of other types remained under the control of individual households) (Evans 1988). From the outset, it was official government policy that the decision to join or leave a cooperative was to be left to the individual households. In practice, however, coercion was often used to encourage people to join a coopera-

tive, and even more so to discourage a household from withdrawing. In late 1978, Stuart-Fox (1980) reported that 1,600 cooperatives had been set up throughout the country, involving 16% of all farming families. The majority were in the provinces of Khammouane and Champassak, in the central and southern parts of the Mekong River Valley. By early 1979, more than 2,500 cooperatives were reported to have been established. However, by mid-1979, it was recognized that the move to collectivization was seriously disrupting production rather than improving it. The disruptive effects on rice production of a severe drought in 1977, followed by a severe flood in 1978, which devastated rice crops in the main rice-growing areas of central and southern Laos, also affected the move to cooperative production. A lack of management skills on the part of officials responsible for the cooperatives was a further major obstacle to both their establishment and operation. In July 1979, a stop was put to the further expansion of the cooperative program, as there was little support for cooperative-based rice production in most rural areas (Stuart-Fox 1980).

Even so, the government restated its commitment to collectivization of production, by emphasizing strengthening existing cooperatives rather than creating new ones. Because of a general lack of enthusiasm and support in many rural areas, from 1979 to 1980 the number of cooperatives dropped by 45% (from about 2,450 to about 1,340) (Table 1). However, official policy still favored the cooperative

Table 1. Expansion of agricultural cooperatives in Laos, 1979-86.

Province	Year							
	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986
Phongsaly	73	152	152	156	167	167	167	167
Luang Namtha	59	74	74	74	74	74	74	69
Oudomxay	72	93	93	98	98	111	115	182
Sayabouly	120	44	44	89	129	160	160	154
Luang Prabang	41	44	44	76	82	98	101	152
Xieng Khouang	200	212	212	252	251	251	247	247
Houaphanh	155	263	263	274	311	311	318	374
Vientiane ^a Municipality	-	-	-	63	104	119	167	192
Vientiane	486	101	101	47	71	93	176	242
Khammouane	433	12	12	24	67	99	104	372
Savannakhet	250	12	12	18	53	164	547	579
Saravane	235	18	18	168	107	216	254	314
Champassak	304	306	306	587	587	597	651	659
Attapeu	24	12	12	12	13	19	19	14
Bokeo ^a	-	-	-	-	-	40	40	67
Borikhamxay ^a	-	-	-	-	-	17	34	76
Sekong ^a	-	-	-	-	-	10	10	120
Total	2,452	1,343	1,352	1,943	2,114	2,546	3,184	3,976

^a-indicates that the administrative area did not exist at the time statistics were recorded. Sources: Evans (1988, 1995).

approach to production and in 1982 some attempt was made to extend cooperative-based rice production to areas of "swidden farming." Tax incentives and preferential terms for access to credit were offered as inducements to encourage rural households to join the cooperative movement. It was reported that, by mid-1984, 37.6% of the farm families and 35.3% of the farming land were involved in 2,402 cooperatives nationwide. The cooperative movement was recorded as having reached its peak in 1986, with almost 4,000 cooperatives being reported as having been established (Table 1). However, several authors (Zasloff 1991, Evans 1995, Stuart-Fox 1997) have indicated that most of these cooperatives existed "in name only," and that in reality there were very few genuine working cooperatives. In fact, the cooperative movement was steadily weakened as members became disillusioned and used their "right to withdraw." The provinces where the cooperative movement was most successful were Champassak, Savannakhet, Xieng Khouang, Saravane, and Sayabouly (Evans 1988). By mid-1988, the government officially recognized the lack of success of the "cooperative concept" under Lao conditions and a decision was made to formally abandon the movement as the basis for improving production. It was acknowledged that the family or individual household unit was a more appropriate basis for achieving both political stability and improved agricultural production, particularly of rice. At about the same time, a number of state farms, which were also established as part of the cooperative movement but that occupied no more than 0.2% of cultivated land, were also privatized, as they were absorbing a disproportionate component of public and other resources (World Bank 1995).

Independent of the cooperative movement (but also influencing it), a significant change in government policy that influenced rice production in the early 1980s was the increased flexibility of pricing and market exchange in the agricultural sector (Evans 1991). In 1980, the prices of most crops and export products were raised by 300% to 500%; retail prices of commodities marketed by the state went up by 200% to 300% and approached paral-

lel market prices. One immediate consequence of these increased incentives was a 16.5% increase in rice production. However, it has also been surmised that some of the production increase reported about this time resulted from changes in tax policy. In 1979, the government replaced the rice output tax with a land tax. One result of this was to remove the incentive to underreport yields and production (though this was replaced by an incentive to underreport the area under cultivation, the basis of the land tax). Although in the early years of the cooperative movement the land of those wishing to withdraw was expropriated, this policy was halted in 1979 and land was returned to those households that had opted to leave the cooperatives. As no general program of land reform had been associated with the cooperative movement, the reversion back to the family unit as the basis of production was not difficult.

Development of irrigated rice production

Farmers throughout Laos have been building traditional weirs and canals for centuries to provide supplementary irrigation to their wet-season rice crops. A typical traditional scheme would include a weir made of logs, stones, and sometimes bamboo and earth, with small hand-dug canals. The command area of these traditional irrigation schemes has varied from a few hectares to about 100 ha, governed mostly by the limited areas of flat land within the mountainous watersheds. These small diversion schemes irrigate terraced or valley-floor paddy fields. As of 2002, thousands of these small weir and canal systems were still in operation in Laos.

Although traditional schemes mainly focus on wet-season rice production, some also produce limited dry-season crops in areas where the streams have a significant dry-season flow, and where farmers have seen the potential for producing additional crops. However, on account of low efficiency levels and high labor demand for frequent repairs of the traditional weirs, over the past 20 years, hundreds of traditional systems have been replaced by more permanent structures.

Irrigation schemes

As recently as 1976, shortly after the LPRP came to power within the country, less than 1% (2,700 ha) of the planted rice area, and less than 1% of rice production (about 3,000 t), was associated with dry-season irrigated cultivation (Table 2). The relatively small irrigated area that existed prior to 1975 was mainly in the form of small weir schemes developed by USAID in the north of the country, particularly in the 1960s.

The first relatively large scheme, about 900 ha in area, also initiated by USAID, was the Faay Namtane scheme in Phiang District of Xayabouly Province. In 1977-78, the expansion of irrigated rice cultivation became one of the agricultural development objectives of the socialist government in its bid to achieve food self-sufficiency (basically rice self-sufficiency), and to reduce the year-to-year vagaries in food production caused by the effects of the weather. This development initiative was closely linked to the policy to develop a national network of agricultural cooperatives as the basis for achieving improvements in agricultural production (Evans 1991).

The first large irrigation schemes to be developed in Laos began in the late 1970s and were located on the floodplains of the Mekong River, not far from the capital, Vientiane. The first of these schemes, the Nam Houm scheme, was implemented through the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in Nasaythong District of Vientiane Municipality. This reservoir-based scheme, whose development commenced in 1977, had a projected capacity of about 3,000 ha of dry-season irrigated crop production. In its development phase, the Mekong Committee provided some financial assistance for the purchase and installation of pumping equipment for the scheme. The second scheme, also initiated in Nasaythong District of Vientiane Municipality, was the Nam Soang scheme. With a projected dry-season irrigation capacity of 4,000 ha, the development of this scheme began in 1978 through the Ministry of De-

fense. Despite the construction of reservoirs, a lack of funds to complete the network of delivery canals resulted in failure to meet the planned irrigation potential of both these schemes, and they did little to improve productivity at the time of their development (World Bank 1995). A lack of appropriate management and technical skills also contributed to the inability to properly develop and use these two schemes.

In the early 1990s, a decision was made to expand the area of rice under irrigated production in order to accelerate improvements in rice production to achieve the joint goals of national rice self-sufficiency and greater production stability. The expanded irrigated production was to focus on developing irrigation schemes that could be used for dry-season cropping activities rather than for wet-season production. However, it was also recognized that the proposed schemes had the potential for wet-season supplementary irrigation use as well. From 1990 to 2001, the dry-season irrigated capacity increased by 750% (from 12,000 to 102,000 ha). Production from the dryseason irrigated environment during this time also increased more than tenfold, from 41,000 to 436,000 t (Table 2).

Most (94.5%) of the expansion in irrigated area took place in the central (70,816 ha) and southern (25,578 ha) agricultural regions. In 2001, still only about 5,600 ha were developed for irrigation in the northern agricultural region. Most of this expansion in irrigated capacity during the 1990s depended on pumping water directly from the Mekong River and, to a lesser extent, from tributaries of the Mekong. There was less investment in the development of appropriate water reticulation systems. However, by 2001, the capacity of these recently developed schemes was being underused because of a combination of factors. Farmer groups were increasingly unable and unwilling to meet the increasing fuel costs of diesel pumps (both diesel and electric pump programs had been installed). This was aggravated by the fact that crop yields were well below the expected potential because of low levels of inputs, particularly fertilizer. In some areas, farmers also encountered difficulties in marketing the second rice crop (the dry-season irrigated crop). Water-use efficiency in many scheme areas was also well below the potential because of a lack of concurrent investment in networks of water distribution canals. Further, farmer organizations, to which responsibility for the pumping schemes was being transferred, did not possess the required skills and resources to maintain the systems. By 2002, it also started to be

Table 2. Development of irrigated rice cultivation, 1976-2002.

	Year/area (000 ha)(% total)				Production (000 t)(% total)			
	Rainfed lowland	Rainfed upland	Irrigated lowland ^a	Total	Rainfed lowland	Rainfed upland	Irrigated lowland ^a	Total
1976	317.7	204.1	2.7	524.5	455	202	3	660
(%)	(60.6)	(38.9)	(0.5)	(100.0)	(68.9)	(30.6)	(0.5)	(100.0)
1978	398.6	216.6	7.5	622.7	508	217	9	734
(%)	(64.0)	(34.8)	(1.2)	(100.0)	(69.2)	(29.6)	(1.2)	(100.0)
1980	426.9	297.4	7.7	732.0	705	337	11	1,053
(%)	(58.3)	(40.6)	(1.1)	(100.0)	(67.0)	(32.0)	(1.1)	(100.0)
1982	435.2	296.2	5.7	737.1	731	349	12	1,092
(%)	(59.0)	(40.2)	(0.8)	(100.0)	(66.9)	(32.0)	(1.1)	(100.0)
1984	360.3	256.2	8.6	625.1	919	380	21	1,320
(%)	(57.6)	(41.0)	(1.4)	(100.0)	(69.6)	(28.8)	(1.6)	(100.0)
1986	385.0	256.6	10.1	651.7	1,082	341	27	1,450
(%)	(59.1)	(39.4)	(1.6)	(100.0)	(74.7)	(23.5)	(1.9)	(100.0)
1988	331.3	213.5	11.4	556.2	686	283	35	1,004
(%)	(59.6)	(38.4)	(2.1)	(100.0)	(68.3)	(28.2)	(3.5)	(100.0)
1990	392.4	245.9	12.0	650.3	1,081	369	41	1,491
(%)	(60.3)	(37.8)	(1.9)	(100.0)	(72.5)	(24.8)	(2.8)	(100.0)
1991	322.8	234.1	13.3	570.2	842	337	44	1,223
(%)	(56.6)	(41.1)	(2.3)	(100.0)	(68.9)	(27.6)	(3.6)	(100.0)
1992	392.5	200.1	15.5	608.1	1,153	292	55	1,500
(%)	(64.6)	(32.9)	(2.5)	(100.0)	(76.9)	(19.5)	(3.7)	(100.0)
1993	350.4	188.3	13.0	551.7	921	284	46	1,251
(%)	(63.5)	(34.1)	(2.7)	(100.0)	(73.6)	(22.7)	(3.7)	(100.0)
1994	380.9	219.1	11.0	611.0	1,198	342	38	1,578
(%)	(62.3)	(35.9)	(1.8)	(100.0)	(75.9)	(21.7)	(2.4)	(100.0)
1995	367.3	179.0	13.6	559.9	1,071	296	50	1,417
(%)	(65.6)	(32.0)	(2.4)	(100.0)	(75.6)	(20.9)	(3.5)	(100.0)
1996	363.1	172.6	18.0	553.7	1,076	266	72	1,414
(%)	(65.6)	(31.2)	(3.3)	(100.0)	(76.1)	(18.8)	(5.1)	(100.0)
1997	421.1	153.6	26.6	601.3	1,300	247	114	1,661
(%)	(70.0)	(25.5)	(4.4)	(100.0)	(78.3)	(14.9)	(6.9)	(100.0)
1998	430.2	134.2	53.1	617.5	1,249	214	212	1,675
(%)	(69.7)	(21.7)	(8.6)	(100.0)	(74.6)	(12.8)	(12.7)	(100.0)
1999	477.2	153.4	87.0	717.6	1,502	247	354	2,103
(%)	(66.5)	(21.4)	(12.1)	(100.0)	(71.4)	(11.8)	(16.8)	(100.0)
2000	475.5	152.1	91.8	719.4	1,553	259	390	2,202
(%)	(66.1)	(21.1)	(12.8)	(100.0)	(70.5)	(11.8)	(17.7)	(100.0)
2001	486.8	158.1	102.0	746.9	1,620	279	436	2,335
(%)	(65.2)	(21.2)	(13.7)	(100.0)	(69.4)	(12.0)	(18.7)	(100.0)
2002	519.5	134.6	84.0	738.1	1,801	240	375	2,416
(%)	(70.4)	(18.2)	(11.4)	(100.0)	(74.6)	(10.0)	(15.5)	(100.0)

^aStatistics represent dry-season

(May-October). Sources: World Bank (1995), Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Vientiane, Lao PDR.

recognized that the dry-season irrigation potential might be better used for crops with higher returns than rice. The 2002-03 dry season therefore saw a significant reduction in the use of the potential of many of the schemes developed during the 1990s.

In 2000, it was estimated that Laos had 22,240 irrigation systems, with a capacity to serve about 280,000 ha in the wet season, or about 36% of the country's 800,000 ha of annually cultivated land. Irrigated land accounted for about 65% of total agricultural production. The majority of the schemes were traditional weirs, some 18,150 in total, located

mostly in mountainous areas, and accounting for about 35% of the total irrigated area.

Since 1975, various agencies have been involved in programs of assistance to improve irrigation capacity within Laos. These agencies are the European Community, United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), United Nations Capital Development Project (UNCDP), Mekong River Commission, Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), the World Bank, the national assistance agencies of Australia and Sweden, and many NGOs.

The impact of natural disasters on rice production

Lao agriculture generally and rice production in particular have always been at the mercy of the weather, bad years being fatalistically accepted along with the good ones. With rice production accounting for more than 80% of the cultivated land area and rice consumption accounting for more than 80% of the calorie intake in many rural areas, the impact of adverse climatic conditions on the livelihood of the Lao people has always been potentially threatening. The occurrence and level of poverty in many areas are recognized as being largely determined by the level and frequency of natural disasters, particularly droughts and floods (ADB 2001).

Droughts and floods

Although detailed historical records on the frequency and severity of droughts and floods do not exist, some severe droughts and their effects were recorded in court chronicles (Stuart-Fox 1998). Recent records clearly indicate the high level of both incidence and significance of floods and droughts. In the 37-year period from 1966 to 2002, for every year, at least part of the country was affected by either drought or flood, or a combination of both (Table 3). The potential impact on rice production was dramatically demonstrated shortly after the LPRP came to power in 1975. As previously noted, in 1977, severe drought conditions throughout the country reduced the national rice harvest by 40% relative to that of 1976 (which was already a year of deficit), with some southern provinces experiencing a decline of up to 95% (Evans 1988). It was estimated that more than 350,000 t of rice aid were required to prevent famine conditions in 1977. In 1978, a disaster of the reverse order—serious flooding—occurred. In some areas of central and southern Laos, crop losses on the order of 90% were reported. At the time, it was estimated that half the population was potentially affected by famine conditions. In both years, without reserve stocks of rice, the government depended on rice donations from the international community to avert potentially serious catastrophes. It was partly in response to the impact of the 1977 and 1978 disasters that the socialist government initiated the agricultural cooperatives movement in an effort to improve rice production and achieve a higher level of rice self-sufficiency. In 1988 and 1989, severe droughts cut annual yield by about one-third, again forcing the government to rely on food aid for its domestic requirements. In

Table 3. Occurrence of damage to rice crops by floods and droughts, 1966-2002.

Year	Type of damage	Region affected
1966	Severe flood	Central
1967	Drought	Central, southern
1968	Flood	Central
1969	Flood	Central
1970	Flood	Central
1971	Severe flood	Central
1972	Flood and drought	Central
1973	Flood	Central
1974	Flood	Southern
1975	Drought	All regions
1976	Flash flood	Central
1977	Severe drought	All regions
1978	Severe flood	Central, southern
1979	Drought and flood	Northern (drought), southern (flood)
1980	Flood	Central
1981	Flood	Central
1982	Drought	All regions
1983	Drought	All regions
1984	Flood	Central, southern
1985	Flash flood	Northern
1986	Flood and drought	Central, southern
1987	Drought	Central, northern
1988	Drought	Southern
1989	Drought	Southern
1990	Flood	Central
1991	Flood and drought	Central
1992	Flood and drought	Central (flood and drought), northern (drought), southern (flood)
1993	Flood and drought	Central, southern
1994	Flood and drought	Central (flood and drought), southern (drought)
1995	Flood	Central, southern
1996	Flash flood, drought	Central
1997	Flood	Central, southern
1998	Drought	All regions
1999	Flood	Central, southern
2000	Flood	Central, southern
2001	Flood	Central, southern
2002	Flood	Central, southern

Source: Unpublished reports of Department of Meteorology, Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.

1988 and 1989, approximately 140,000 t of rice were donated or sold to Laos (Hopkins 1995).

More recently, in 8 of the 12 years from 1991 to 2002, significant areas of lowland rice in the Mekong River Valley were destroyed by floods (Table 4). In 1991, more than 21% (about 70,000 ha) of the rice area was destroyed; in 1995, almost 30% of the planted area in the central agricultural region was destroyed; whereas, in 1996, 17.5% and 18.7% of the rice area in the central and southern agricultural regions, respectively, were destroyed. As periods of submersion associated with the flooding of the Mekong River can often extend beyond 2 weeks, total crop loss usually results in areas affected by flooding. Some areas particularly prone to flooding have

Table 4. Wet-season lowland crop losses (ha destroyed) due to flood damage, 1991-2002.

Region	Year							
	1991a	1994	1995	1996	1997	2000	2001	2002
Central								
(ha)		28,783	55,061	41,863	26,300	28,350	30,193	24,151
(%)		(13.7)	(29.0)	(17.5)	(10.2)	(10.6)	(11.4)	(8.5)
Southern								
(ha)		3,135	5,759	23,720	6,750	14,530	11,790	8,103
(%)		(2.6)	(4.9)	(18.7)	(5.2)	(11.0)	(8.2)	(5.3)
Northern								
(ha)		4,464	1,500	354	225	20	240	1,810
(%)		(8.3)	(2.5)	(0.5)	(0.3)	(<0.1)	(0.3)	(2.2)
Total								
(ha)	70,000	36,382	62,820	65,937	33,275	42,900	42,223	34,064
(%)	(21.3)	(9.5)	(16.9)	(15.3)	(7.9)	(9.0)	(8.7)	(6.6)

^aRegional flood damage data are unavailable. Sources: Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry and the Ministry of Labor and Social Welfare.

recently been withdrawn from wet-season cropping activities following the development and expansion of the potential for dry-season irrigated cropping. Flooding in the northern mountainous agricultural region is usually of short duration and crops can sometimes recover from the impact of such floods; however, the nature of floods is such that they are potentially capable of causing significant levels of soil erosion, particularly in areas with a history of intensive slash-and-burn agriculture.

Drought, although less spectacular than devastating floods, is a regular occurrence throughout the rice-growing areas of Laos (Table 3). Farmers in the rainfed lowland environment of the Mekong River Valley consider drought as their most consistent production constraint (Khotsimuang et al 1995). The soils in this region are predominantly loams, sandy loams, and sands, and are particularly drought-prone (Lathvilayvong et al 1996). Although the effects of drought can often be less severe than those of floods, drought usually affects a much larger area than floods. Both early and late wet-season droughts occur and affect rice production (Fukai et al 1998). Early-season drought usually occurs from mid-June to mid-July as the monsoons change from southeast to southwest. The effects of this type of drought can be reduced by appropriate crop management practices, particularly by matching crop phenology with water availability (Fukai et al 1998). Late-season drought occurs if the regular monsoon rains end early. Fukai et al (1995) have demonstrated that late-season drought alone can reduce grain yields by an average of 30%. The use of earlier maturing improved varieties to replace later maturing, and often lower yielding,

traditional varieties can significantly reduce the potential impact of late-season drought. Fukai et al (1998) also demonstrated that the effect of drought on grain yield also depends on soil fertility, and that improved soil fertility increases grain yield, even in drought-affected seasons.

The occurrence of drought in uplands is equally as frequent and can be equally as severe as in lowlands. Lebar and Suddard (1960) reported on the occurrence of a serious drought throughout much of northern Laos in 1955, the severity of which was so great that rice was flown in on U.S. planes and dropped by parachute to villagers in order to avert potential starvation. Although ranked third among production constraints by upland farmers (Roder et al 1997), the impact of drought in the upland environment is of increasing significance and concern. Dry conditions in this environment have the greatest impact when occurring at or about the time of dry-seeding, affecting both germination and establishment. Late-season drought (i.e., when the wet-season rains end early) is not normally a concern, as most upland crops are harvested 30 to 50 days earlier than lowland crops in the same region.

Even with the recent increase in the area of cultivation under irrigated conditions (Table 2), the majority of both the planted area and production in Laos will remain at the mercy of the vagaries of the weather for the foreseeable future. However, it is possible to achieve greater yield stability under such conditions through varietal improvement.

Biotic disasters

Pests and diseases are also chronic production constraints for both upland and lowland environments (Schiller et al 2001). Normally, their impact is relatively localized and often the implementation of appropriate management practices can minimize their potential damage to rice crops. However, one category of pest in upland environments that has traditionally had an impact on production often of the same magnitude as

natural disasters is rodents (Roder et al 1997, Singleton et al 1999). Although actual grain losses due to rodents have yet to be quantified, it is estimated that they probably account for at least 15% of the annual rice harvest (Singleton and Petch 1994). At irregular intervals, conditions favor massive rodent population explosions, resulting in local losses of more than 50% of the rice crop. Occasionally, entire rice crops are lost, as happened in parts of Luang Prabang Province in 1991.

National rice sufficiency

Rice production in Laos has generally been on the basis of meeting immediate household needs. In the absence of an established market for rice, until recently, there has been little incentive to produce a rice surplus, particularly under upland conditions. As a result, small fluctuations in yield caused by climate, pest problems, or labor shortages have usually been immediately reflected in rice shortages (Roder et al 1996). These authors also report that occasional shortages of rice are not a recent phenomenon. Observations in the uplands as long ago as the early 1940s report rice stores often being empty in July, forcing farming families to rely on hunting and gathering for provisions for periods of 3–4 months before the harvest of the next rice crop.

Independent of the impact of the vagaries of the weather and pest problems, changes in the level of rice self-sufficiency have, until relatively recently, often reflected the level of political stability throughout the country. During the period of French administration from 1893 to 1945, there was considerable resistance of many ethnic groups

to a number of government policies. In particular, resistance was strong to some of the taxation measures, as well as the system of annual unpaid labor that was imposed (Batson 1991, Simms and Simms 1999). The often physical resistance of some ethnic groups to the implementation of these laws and measures was associated with a lack of stability in many upland areas, which interrupted normal upland rice-cropping cycles. As a result, during the period of French administration, significant areas of Laos often had periodic and chronic rice shortages because of factors other than the impact of natural disasters and pest damage. Total annual rice production during this period fluctuated from a maximum of just over 500,000 t in 1923 to an average of less than 300,000 t during the 1930s. In upland areas, shortages were made up by maize (from upland swiddens) and various tuber crops. However, in lowland areas, the deficits were not so readily replaced by alternative foods. A 20% decline in the national rice harvest in 1936 was associated with subsequent near-starvation conditions in parts of Khammouane Province. After Lao independence in 1953, under the Royal Lao government there was a 20-year period during which the disruptive effects of the ongoing civil conflict in much of the country also disrupted the normal rice-cropping cycles, in both upland and lowland environments. For much of this time, there was a chronic national rice deficit, with shortages at both regional and local levels often being critical. In the upland environment, the frequent displacement of villages in some areas generally meant that the rice shortages were more acute than in lowland areas. At the height of the conflict

in the 1960s and early 1970s, tens of thousands of members of mainly upland ethnic groups fled their villages to avoid the fighting in the north of the country, while the Plain of Jars in the northeastern region was almost depopulated (Stuart-Fox 1997). Stuart-Fox (1997) reports that during this time “as many as three-quarters of a million people, a quarter of the entire population, had been driven from their homes to become refugees in their own country.” In some remote areas, displaced villages became totally dependent on food supplies dropped by American planes. At the peak of the shortages in the early 1970s, more than 170,000 refugees were understood to be dependent on receiving rice in this way in the north of the country alone. The rice used for these “sky drops” was all imported. It was even reported that some young children of this era came to believe that “rice came from the sky.” Appa Rao et al report that some of this “rice from the sky” was used as seed for planting, and was still being planted at the time varieties were collected for conservation and preservation in the latter part of the 1990s, having been given the varietal name “American rice.” Batson (1991) reports that it was not until 1984 that some degree of national rice self-sufficiency was first achieved. However, even for that year, the same author noted that “a combination of uneven production, poor land, poor transportation, and climatic vagaries left people in the rugged, highland areas without enough rice or with very marginal surpluses.”

In the main areas of lowland rice cultivation, rice self-sufficiency from year to year has primarily reflected the occurrence of natural disasters—droughts and floods, and occasionally pest and disease problems. At a national level, the decision in the early 1990s to expand the area of irrigated rice production has, in association with the adoption of improved production practices in lowland environments, brought about a rapid change in the reported level of national rice self-sufficiency. Production from the 2001 dry-season irrigated environment accounted for about 19% of total production for that year, compared with less than 3% coming from the irrigated environment in 1990.

Although the official statistics of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry indicated that national rice self-sufficiency was achieved in 1999 with the production of 2.1 million tons of paddy rice (Table 2), with further increases in subsequent years to in excess of 2.4 million tons in 2002, unofficially it is acknowledged that these figures are overestimates. It has also been long acknowledged that national rice

Table 5. Levels of rice sufficiency (months per year) according to region and ethnicity.

Region	Ethnicity			
	Mon-Khmer	Tibeto-Burman	Hmong-Mien	Lao-Tai
North	6.2	7.0	8.2	11.5
East	6.3	—	7.8	6.5
Central	7.9	—	8.0	10.8
South	5.5	—	—	9.3
Average	5.9	7.0	8.1	9.0

Source: UNDP (2002).

self-sufficiency does not necessarily translate into regional, provincial, or household self-sufficiency. Rice surpluses of recent years in areas with double-cropping potential as a result of the expansion of irrigated rice cultivation have not necessarily alleviated the increasing chronic rice shortages of many upland areas. Recent studies on poverty and human development in Laos (ADB 2001, UNDP 2000) reveal that 90% of villages classified as poor throughout the country depend on swidden agriculture as their primary means of livelihood. Levels of poverty are closely linked to levels of food (primarily rice) sufficiency. Generally speaking, the level of rice deficiency is currently greatest within Mon-Khmer groups in upland areas and least in the Tai-Lao, who predominately inhabit the lowlands (Table 5). Rice shortages in the uplands generally average 3–4 months but can be as much as 8 months and are chronic; in the lowlands, they average 1–3 months and vary from year to year, depending on natural disasters, particularly drought and floods, and place to place, reflecting irrigation potential and the availability of land.

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